

What the Func? Multiple Realizability Need not be Vague

Olivia Guest^{1,2}, Mark Blokpoel^{1,2}, and Iris van Rooij^{1,2,3}

¹Department of Cognitive Science and Artificial Intelligence, Radboud University, The Netherlands

²Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition, and Behaviour, Radboud University, The Netherlands

³Department of Linguistics, Cognitive Science, and Semiotics, Aarhus University, Denmark

Abstract

Multiple realizability (MR) is *not* necessarily unclear *nor* does it purely operate at the computational level. To understand potential relationships between MR and other constraints, such as metabolic, we formalise possible meanings of function in cognitive science. We build on these to formalise MR, thus resolving its apparent vagaries. Importantly, MR formalisms meaningfully guide and constrain theory building.

Haueis and Colaço (2025) rightly point out that resource considerations constrain the space of possible and plausible models (viz. Blokpoel, 2018; van Rooij, 2008; van Rooij & Baggio, 2021; van Rooij et al., 2019). Yet, multiple realizability (MR) remains an intrinsic feature of explanatory models. We offer a complementary but different view on MR, to demonstrate that it does not deal in vagaries nor exist solely at the computational level, and is a productive part of modeling.

First, notions of MR have existed for millennia. Voula Tsouna (2023) explains: “Epicurus’ conception of the *pollachos tropos* [method of multiple explanations] is rich, nuanced, fairly coherent, and strongly motivated by methodological and scientific considerations” (p. 240). Epicurians contemplated celestial phenomena, but the argument applies to cognitive neuroscience: “there are in-principle reasons why explanatory pluralism is to be expected[:] the computational description is no more and no less realistic and fundamental than the mechanistic/implementational one” (Chirimuuta, 2018, p. 406).

Second, we define four distinct notions of function: ϕ , T , G , and τ . A function $F : I \rightarrow O$ maps elements in the set I to elements in the set O . Importantly, functions are not guaranteed to be computable. And for any given computable function there exist many algorithms. This is an instance of MR at the algorithmic level to which we return below. Before that, what could a function be?

Functional capacity ϕ : A system \mathbb{S} (modeled by \mathbb{M} , see Figure 1) may be held to have some purported functional capacity, denoted by $\phi : I_\phi \rightarrow O_\phi$. For instance, a person, brain, or component may be believed to have the capacity for addition, ϕ .

Functional theory T : A theorist may specify a functional theory for a purported capacity ϕ using a well-defined function, $T : I_T \rightarrow O_T$ (Egan, 2017). For instance, $T : \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ with $T(a, b) = a + b$ where $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$ may model the functional capacity for addition ϕ .

Figure 1. Relationships between the system under study \mathbb{S} and models \mathbb{M} . The single solid line is relationships within the neurocognitive system. Double solid lines represent the theoretical mapping proposed between \mathbb{S} to \mathbb{M} . The dashed line links \mathbb{M} to its digital substrate. Dotted lines represent relationships to lower substrates.

Functional goal G : An algorithmic model A may be designed or tuned (e.g., so-called ‘training’ of artificial neural network models; Guest & Martin, 2023, 2025b) to perform a given goal capacity, denoted $G : I_G \rightarrow O_G$. We say A (approximately) computes functional goal G if and only if $A(i) \approx G(i)$ (cf. Blokpoel, 2018; van Rooij & Wareham, 2012). When $G = T$, then A could be an algorithmic-level explanation for functional theory T .

Functional role τ : A functional capacity ϕ (modeled by T) may be hypothesized to play functional role $\tau : I_\tau \rightarrow O_\tau$. For instance, adding may aggregate synaptic inputs or determine the cost of groceries. A capacity ϕ (modeled by T) fulfils a functional role if and only if it can behave consistently with the teleological specification, i.e., $\phi(i) \equiv T(i) = \tau(i)$, for all $i \in I_\phi = I_T \supseteq I_\tau$.

All models ϕ , T , G and τ , are defined by the scientist. Knowledge obtained from experiments may be used to *abduce* candidate theories T of ϕ , but not to *deduce* them. In contrast, τ is definitionally *prima facie* assigned to \mathbb{S} ’s ϕ ; and only unassigned if the system is deemed to have broken down (Egan, 2017, 2025). An example from biology for τ is that the function of the heart is to pump blood; perhaps less useful for cognitive science under computationalism as it results in truism, such as the purpose of vision is to see.

Next, we offer MR formalisms.

MR $_\phi$: A functional role τ is said to be *multiply ϕ -realizable* if and only if there can in principle exist multiple distinct functional capacities ϕ_1, ϕ_2, \dots (modeled by T_1, T_2, \dots) that fulfil that role τ in some possible world. We furthermore say τ is *multiply ϕ -realized* if there exists more than one such capacity in our world. For example, if one wants to soft-boil an egg for 6 minutes, and knows there are 6 minutes left on a video one is currently watching, then one can use the video player as a timer.

MR $_m$: A functional capacity ϕ is said to be *multiply m -realizable* if and only if there can,

in principle, exists multiple distinct mechanisms m_1, m_2, \dots that have that capacity ϕ in some possible world. We furthermore say ϕ is *multiply m-realized* if there exists more than one such mechanism in our world; recall [Figure 1](#) and bear in mind that substrates do not (straightforwardly) cut it as mechanisms under computationalism (Guest & Martin, 2025a). For example, the capacity for addition can be performed in the head, using a calculator, or on an abacus (Guest, 2025). Here m may refer to the algorithm, the physical implementation, or both.

By abuse of terminology, we may also say that a functional role τ can be *multiply m-realizable* if there exist mechanisms m_1, m_2, \dots that can realize one or more ϕ that can realize functional role τ . For example, a timer can be instantiated in a wall clock, a software stopwatch, or as above the video player.

Finally, these meanings of MR demonstrate that it need not be vague nor operating only at the computational level (also see Chirimuuta, 2018; Egan, 2017; Figdor, 2010; Hardcastle, 1995; Litch, 1997; Polger & Shapiro, 2016; Ross, 2020). MR operates at each level. That is, a particular functional role can be performed by different functional capacities. Functional capacities can be realized by different algorithms. A particular algorithm can be physically realized in different ways.

Any serious proposals for metabolic additions under computationalism will need to contend with MR — at the level and type the modeler defines — not because MR and metabolism have something specific to say about each other but because *both* are relevant. We thus urge and support theorists to take seriously their commitments to MR by providing these formal tools, which help think through what our formal models imply.

References

- Blokpoel, M. (2018). Sculpting Computational-Level Models. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, 10(3), 641–648. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12282>
- Chirimuuta, M. (2018). Marr, Mayr, and MR: What functionalism should now be about. *Philosophical Psychology*, 31(3), 403–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09515089.2017.1381679>
- Egan, F. (2017). Function-theoretic explanation and the search for neural mechanisms. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780199685509.003.0007>
- Egan, F. (2025). *Deflating mental representation*. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/15666.001.0001>
- Figdor, C. (2010). Neuroscience and the multiple realization of cognitive functions. *Philosophy of Science*, 77(3), 419–456. <https://doi.org/10.1086/652964>
- Guest, O. (2025). What Does ‘Human-Centred AI’ Mean? <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.19960>
- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2023). On logical inference over brains, behaviour, and artificial neural networks. *Computational Brain & Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42113-022-00166-x>
- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2025a). Are neurocognitive representations ‘small cakes’? <https://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/24834/>

- Guest, O., & Martin, A. E. (2025b). A metatheory of classical and modern connectionism. *Psychological Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000591>
- Hardcastle, V. G. (1995). Computationalism. *Synthese*, *105*, 303–317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01063561>
- Haueis, P., & Colaço, D. J. (2025). Metabolic considerations for cognitive modeling. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 1–53. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0140525x25103956>
- Litch, M. (1997). Computation, connectionism and modelling the mind. *Philosophical Psychology*, *10*(3), 357–364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09515089708573225>
- Polger, T. W., & Shapiro, L. A. (2016). *The multiple realization book*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198732891.001.0001>
- Ross, L. N. (2020). Multiple realizability from a causal perspective. *Philosophy of Science*, *87*(4), 640–662. <https://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/16476/>
- Tsouna, V. (2023). The method of multiple explanations revisited. In *Epicureanism and scientific debates. antiquity and late reception: Volume i. language, medicine, meteorology* (pp. 221–256). Leuven University Press. Retrieved March 21, 2026, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv34h08cj.13>
- van Rooij, I. (2008). The tractable cognition thesis. *Cognitive science*, *32*(6), 939–984. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03640210801897856>
- van Rooij, I., & Baggio, G. (2021). Theory before the test: How to build high-verisimilitude explanatory theories in psychological science. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, *16*(4), 682–697. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620970604>
- van Rooij, I., Blokpoel, M., Kwisthout, J., & Wareham, T. (2019). *Cognition and intractability: A guide to classical and parameterized complexity analysis*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781107358331>
- van Rooij, I., & Wareham, T. (2012). Intractability and approximation of optimization theories of cognition. *Journal of Mathematical Psychology*, *56*(4), 232–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmp.2012.05.002>